

Synthesis of Some 5-Arylazo-6-(substituted amino) Pyrimidines

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Synthesis of some 2,4-diamino-6-(substituted amino)-, 2,4-dihydroxy-6-(substituted amino)-, 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-(substituted amino)-, 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-(substituted amino)-pyrimidines having phenylazo or *p*-chlorophenylazo group in the 5-position is described. The synthesis of 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-anilinopyrimidine is also reported.

2,4-Diamino-5-arylazopyrimidines can be looked up as uncyclized analogues of 2,4-diaminopteridines which are known to have high antifolic acid activity in various bacterial

	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
IIa	NH ₂	NH ₂	<i>p</i> -I-C ₆ H ₄ -NH-	Cl
IIb	NH ₂	NH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ NH-	Cl
IIc	NH ₂	NH ₂	C ₆ H ₁₁ NH-*	Cl
IId	NH ₂	NH ₂	C ₅ H ₁₀ N-**	Cl
IIe	NH ₂	NH ₂	C ₆ H ₁₀ N-**	H
IIf	OH	OH	C ₆ H ₅ NH-	Cl
IIg	OH	OH	C ₆ H ₁₁ NH-*	Cl
IIh	OH	OH	C ₅ H ₁₀ N-**	Cl
IIi	OH	OH	C ₆ H ₅ NH-	H
IIj	NH ₂	OH	C ₆ H ₅ NH-	Cl
IIk	NH ₂	OH	C ₆ H ₁₁ NH-*	Cl
IIl	NH ₂	OH	C ₅ H ₁₀ N-**	Cl
IIm	OH	NH ₂	C ₆ H ₅ NH-	Cl
IIn	OH	NH ₂	C ₆ H ₁₁ NH-*	Cl
IIo	OH	NH ₂	C ₅ H ₁₀ N-**	Cl

* Cyclohexylamino

** Piperidino

systems. Several workers¹⁻⁷ have synthesized a number of 5-arylazopyrimidines and found that many of them possess interesting antifolic, antimicrobial and antineoplastic properties.

A number of pyrimidines having an amino and/or hydroxyl group at C₂ and C₄ positions and a bulky substituted amino group at C₆ position have been found to inhibit the growth of some microorganisms⁸⁻¹¹. We were interested in studying the effect of introducing an arylazo group in the 5-position of the above type of compounds on their biological properties. In the present paper we describe the synthesis of a number of such compounds (compounds IIa-II₀).

The new 5-arylazopyrimidines were obtained by the reaction of an appropriate 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyrimidine (I) with diazotized *p*-chloroaniline or aniline. The coupling reaction was carried out at a temperature of 2-5° and at slightly acidic *pH* (*pH* 5-6) or slightly alkaline *pH* (*pH* 8-9) depending on the nature of the 5-unsubstituted pyrimidine compound. Proper maintenance of *pH* was found essential for the reaction.

One unknown parent compound 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-anilinopyrimidine was also synthesized by the action of aniline on 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine¹⁶ in presence of a few drops of conc. HCl.

The 5-arylazopyrimidines are in general coloured crystalline substances insoluble in common organic solvents. Their method of preparation and spectral and other properties studied are indicated in the Table 1.

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TABLE I

5-Arylazopyrimidines (IIa-IIo) synthesized^a

Com- pound	Method of preparation ^b (Yield %)	Melting point (colour)	Molecular formula	Analysis %		Absorption	
				Found	Required	λ_{\max} m μ	log ϵ
IIa	A (84)	290-1°(d) (Yellow needles)	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₇ Cl	C : 41.24	41.29	210	4.46
				H : 3.27	2.79	255	4.28
				N : 21.26	21.07	290	4.49
						430*	4.44
IIb	B (83)	253-4° (Yellow needles)	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ Cl	C : 56.67	56.56	210	4.29
				H : 4.49	4.12	250	4.16
				N : 28.54	28.87	285	4.35
						433*	4.38
IIc	C (70)	207-8° (Yellowish orange needles)	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₇ Cl	C : 55.38	55.65	215	4.30
				H : 6.17	5.79	257	4.26
				N : 28.04	28.40	395*	4.42
IIc	B (82)	208-9° (Reddish orange)	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₇ Cl	C : 54.61	54.31	216	4.21
				H : 5.62	5.43	230	4.20
				N : 29.45	29.56	273	4.19
						396*	4.35
IIe	B (77)	178-9° (Orange plates)	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₇	C : 60.92	60.60	208	4.08
				H : 6.30	6.36	216**	4.15
				N : 32.77	32.99	235	4.19
						275	4.20
						390*	4.33
IIf	D (73)	271-2°(d) (Yellowish brown needles)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₂ Cl	C : 56.23	56.22	206	4.24
				H : 4.07	3.51	250	4.31
				N : 20.65	20.49	405*	4.41
IIg	D (83)	256-7° (Yellow needles)	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ Cl	C : 55.61	55.33	215	4.29
				H : 5.78	5.18	405*	4.40
				N : 19.78	20.15		
IIh	D (70)	260-1°(d) (Yellow needles)	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₂ Cl	C : 54.03	54.05	205**	4.02
				H : 5.13	4.80	230	4.39
				N : 20.97	21.02	400*	4.43

TABLE 1—(contd.)

5-Arylazopyrimidines (IIa-IIo) synthesized^a

Com- pound	Method of preparation ^b (Yield %)	Melting point (colour)	Molecular formula	Analysis %		Absorption	
				Found	Required	λ_{\max} $m\mu$	$\log \epsilon$
IIi	D (66)	307-8°(d) (Yellow)	$C_{16}H_{13}N_5O_2$	C : 62.53	62.55	205	3.98
				H : 4.57	4.23	207	4.00
				N : 22.58	22.80	215*	4.04
						281	4.18
						395*	4.14
IIj	E (71)	303-4°(d) (Golden Yellow needles) ^c	$C_{16}H_{13}N_6OCl$	C : 56.61	56.39	213	4.11
				H : 4.08	3.80	245	4.21
				N : 24.28	24.67	285	4.28
						400*	4.33
IIk	E (53)	305-6°(d) (Yellow needles)	$C_{16}H_{13}N_6OCl$	C : 55.15	55.42	217	4.43
				H : 5.32	5.48	245*	4.24
				N : 24.23	24.24	390*	4.41
III	B (76)	255-6°(d) (Yellowish orange needles)	$C_{15}H_{17}N_6OCl$	C : 54.30	54.16	205**	4.13
				H : 5.53	5.11	224	4.30
				N : 25.70	25.27	300*	3.85
						415*	4.43
IIIm*	B (65)	308-9°(d) (Yellowish orange)	$C_{16}H_{13}N_6OCl$, C_2H_5OH	C : 55.39	55.89	215	4.12
				H : 4.56	4.90	247	4.23
				N : 21.72	21.73	295	4.34
						390*	4.32
IIIn	F (71)	301-2°(d) (Yellow)	$C_{16}H_{13}N_6OCl$	C : 55.81	55.42	225	4.33
				H : 5.91	5.48	273	4.09
				N : 24.60	24.24	385	4.39
IIo	E (83)	280-1°(d) (Golden yellow)	$C_{15}H_{17}N_6OCl$	C : 54.50	54.16	205**	4.08
				H : 5.46	5.11	242	4.35
				N : 25.17	25.27	285	4.12
						385	4.30

a. Compound IIe was crystallized from water-alcohol (1 : 1), IIj from pyridine-water (1 : 1), IIk from pyridine-water (1 : 2) and IIo from pyridine. IIIi was purified by dissolving it in 6N NH_4OH aq. at room temperature and reprecipitating with glacial acetic acid. All other compounds were crystallized from alcohol.

b. See under Experimental.

c. It becomes reddish orange on drying at 80° or on standing.

[†]It crystallized as monoalcoholate.

* Broad band.

** Very inconspicuous.

Among the compounds synthesized compound IIc, IId, IIe, IIf, IIh, IIIi, and IIIk showed antifolic acid activity and significant inhibitory effects on the growth of *S. faecalis*.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a copper block. Melting point of compounds that melted with decomposition was determined by rapidly heating the block to about 20° below the actual melting point and then heating the block at the rate of ca 4°/min. All the melting points reported are "corrected".

In crystallization, the term "alcohol" always refers to 95% (w/w) ethanol.

Absorption spectra of the compounds were determined in absolute alcohol in 1 cm. cell in the Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer.

For analysis the compounds were dried over phosphorus pentoxide at 110°/1 mm. for 16 hr.

Starting materials : The following starting materials were used for the synthesis of the 5-arylaazo compounds :

2,4-Diamino-6-*p*-iodoanilinopyrimidine¹¹; 2,4-diamino-6-anilinopyrimidine¹²; 2,4-diamino-6-cyclohexylaminopyrimidinehydrochloride¹¹; 2,4-diamino-6-piperidinopyrimidine^{10,13}; 2,4-dihydroxy-6-anilinopyrimidine¹⁴; 2,4-dihydroxy-6-cyclohexylaminopyrimidine¹⁴; 2,4-dihydroxy-6-piperidinopyrimidine¹⁴; 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-anilinopyrimidine^{8*}; 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-cyclohexylaminopyrimidine^{10,15}; 2-amino-4-hydroxy-6-piperidinopyrimidine¹¹; 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-cyclohexylaminopyrimidine¹¹; 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-piperidinopyrimidine¹¹ and 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-anilinopyrimidine (preparation of which is given below)

2-Hydroxy-4-amino-6-anilinopyrimidine (I, R = OH, R₁ = NH₂, R₂ = C₆H₅NH-) : To a solution of 2-hydroxy-4-amino-6-chloropyrimidine¹⁶ (1.0 g, 0.0068M) in hot water-ethanol mixture (2 : 1, 55 ml), aniline (0.93 g, 0.01M) and conc. HCl (4 drops) were added and the resulting solution was refluxed for 1 hr. On cooling to room temperature a white precipitate appeared. The precipitation was completed by neutralization with dil. alkali (to pH 7). The precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried at 60° and crystallized from alcohol water (3 : 2) mixture. White crystals yield 1.15 g (83%), m.p. 337-9° (d). Absorption λ_{max} 215 mμ, 290 mμ (log ε 4.19, 4.33 respectively). (Found C : 59.12, H : 4.63, N : 27.99%. C₁₀H₁₀N₄O requires C : 59.40, H : 4.97, N : 27.72%).

General methods for the preparation of arylazopyrimidines :

Method A : 2,4,6-Trisubstituted pyrimidine derivative (0.2 g) was suspended in water (40 ml) and glacial acetic acid was added drop by drop until a clear solution was obtained. The solution was cooled in ice-water and a cold solution of an equimolecular amount of the

* For this compound, we have observed a m.p. 259-60° (Lit. 145°).

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corresponding benzenediazonium chloride in 1*N* HCl aq. [prepared by adding a cold solution of sodium nitrate in water (2 ml) with stirring to an ice-cold solution of the aromatic amine in 1*N* HCl aq. (4 ml). Equivalent amounts of sodium nitrite and the aromatic amine were used in order to avoid excess of nitrous acid. The diazotized solution must contain excess of HCl.] was slowly added with stirring. The stirring was continued and after 5 min. 1*N* NaOH aq. was added to bring the *pH* of the solution to 8–9, when a heavy coloured precipitate appeared. Stirring was then continued for four more hours. The mixture was cooled in ice-water all through. The reaction mixture was kept in there frigerator overnight. The crude product was filtered, washed with water, dried at 80° and then purified by crystallization.

Method B : This was similar to the method A except that the starting pyrimidine was dissolved in water (20 ml.) containing a few drops of 1*N* HCl aq.

Method C : This was similar to the method A except that the starting pyrimidine (in the form of hydrochloride) was dissolved in water (20 ml.).

Method D : 2,4,6-Trisubstituted pyrimidine (0.2 g) was suspended in water (20 ml.) and 2*N* NaOH aq. was added with stirring until a clear solution was obtained. The solution was cooled in ice-water and a cold solution of an equimolecular amount of the corresponding benzenediazonium chloride in 1*N* HCl aq. (prepared as before) was slowly added with stirring. The stirring was continued and after 5 min. the *pH* of the solution was brought to 6 by adding 1*N* NaOH aq. or 1*N* HCl aq. Stirring was then continued for 4 more hr. The mixture was cooled in ice-water all through. The reaction mixture was kept in the refrigerator overnight. The crude product was filtered, washed with water, dried at 80° and purified by crystallization.

Method E : This was similar to the method D except that the starting pyrimidine was dissolved in water (20 ml.) by addition of a few drops of 1*N* HCl aq.

Method F : 2,4,6-Trisubstituted pyrimidine (0.2 g) was suspended in water (20 ml.) and 1*N* HCl aq. was added drop by drop until a clear solution was obtained. The solution was cooled in ice-water and a cold solution of an equimolecular amount of *p*-chlorobenzene-diazonium chloride in 1*N* HCl aq. (prepared as before) was slowly added with stirring. The stirring was continued and after 5 min. 1*N* NaOH aq. was added to bring the *pH* of the solution to 8–9 and at this *pH* the solution was stirred for 5 min., when a heavy yellow-orange precipitate was obtained. Then the *pH* of the solution was brought to 6 by adding 1*N* HCl aq. and stirring was continued at this *pH* for 4 more hr. The mixture was cooled in ice-water all through. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in the refrigerator. The product was filtered, washed with water, dried at 80° and purified by crystallization.

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